

13th hranom do zdravlja with food to health

Book of Abstracts of the 13th International
Scientific and Professional Conference
WITH FOOD TO HEALTH

Knjiga sažetaka s 13. međunarodnog
znanstveno-stručnog skupa
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**IMPACT OF ENZYME AND MICROWAVE PRETREATMENTS ON THE
SUPERCRITICAL CARBON DIOXIDE EXTRACTION OF *Origanum
vulgare***

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poster presentation

Aromatic medicinal plant oregano (*Origanum vulgare*) represents a highly important natural resource widely used in the production of food, flavour, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical products. Given the importance of oregano lipophilic bioactive components and their high applicability and demand, there is a constant need for improving technologies for their recovery.

A technology that has been established as a green approach for obtaining lipophilic compounds from natural resources is supercritical carbon dioxide (ScCO₂) extraction. To achieve rational exploitation of material and increase extraction efficiency, enzymatic and microwave pretreatments of the *O. vulgare* herbal material were applied.

The ScCO₂ extraction was performed at 40 °C and 200 bar. For the enzymatic pretreatment, the cellulolytic enzyme mixture was used, whereas the microwave pretreatment was conducted using 360 W for 2 min. Presence of 20 components was detected in the aromatic profiles of extracts, among which the most dominant component was carvacrol in the 68-80% range. The application of the pretreatments resulted in the disruption of the cellular structure of the plant material and a greater release of lipophilic components, compared to the control (extraction without pretreatment). Moreover, the enzymatic pretreatment increased the extraction yield by 48.51%, while the microwave pretreatment achieved a 53.2% higher yield.

Keywords: oregano, aroma, supercritical carbon dioxide, enzymatic pretreatment; microwave

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